

Information and disinformation in video gaming

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Video games, Information Behaviour

STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

This paper aims to identify how player-created in-game information in video games may be used creatively to both inform and misinform other players. Findings from four small scale investigations into players' information behaviour (IB) (Fan, 2023; Meng, 2022; Tang, 2022; Wang, 2023) are presented to identify how textual, visual and auditory information is used within games.

Value of the contribution

The paper contributes to knowledge about how players engage with information within video games. Video games are an increasingly popular leisure activity: Statista (2024) estimates there will be 2.6 billion players worldwide in 2025. While there have been studies of peer-created information external to the game (e.g. Harviainen et al, 2012; Sköld, 2017), there are still few studies of player-created in-game information (as opposed to designer-produced information as in e.g. Urban, 2021).

Research outline

Results drawn from four unpublished Masters dissertations are presented, all supervised by the author. Each research study received ethics approval, and participants consented for use of their data for further publication. The definition of IB underpinning the studies is that of Wilson (2000): "the totality of human behavior in relation to sources and channels of information, including both active and passive information seeking, and information use."

Fan (2023) and Tang (2022) each interviewed seven Chinese players of Elden Ring, to investigate their IB. Meng (2022) and Wang (2023) both investigated social deduction games; Meng (2022) gathering 164 questionnaires and carrying out six interviews with Chinese players of Dread Hunger, and Wang carrying out 11 interviews with Chinese players of Goose, Goose, Duck. The focus in this paper is primarily on the interview data. Participants were aged 18 years or older and interviewed online in Chinese using

Google Meet, Zoom or MS Teams. The researchers were all experienced players of the games they investigated and recruited participants through a snowballing approach. Interviews were transcribed and analysed thematically in Chinese and then English. The author identified further themes across the four dissertations' findings. Elden Ring (<https://en.bandainamcoent.eu/elden-ring/elden-ring>) is an action RPG (Role Play Game) with an open world which players explore to complete quests. It can be played solo, but also has an asynchronous multiplayer mode, which enables a distinctive feature whereby players can leave messages for others to discover. There are limits on the size of the message and the words that can be used, but players use their ingenuity to overcome these limits to leave helpful, amusing or misleading messages (Smith Nicholls & Cook, 2022). The messages can be left in the game landscape. Examples can be seen in MecClesky (2022) and Moe Gaming (2022). Social deduction games are multiplayer, with one or more players as villains secretly aiming to eliminate the other players, and remaining players as innocents who need to unmask the villain before they are killed. In *Goose, Goose, Duck* (<https://gaggle.fun/goose-goose-duck>) the villain is a duck disguised as a Goose. In *Dread Hunger* (Wikimedia, 2025) a ship is trapped in the Arctic, and the crew must escape and also work out who amongst them are the two traitorous killers. Research into social deduction games has included investigating ways of detecting player roles (e.g. Tuin & Rooijackers, 2021) and analysing speech to detect liars (e.g. Zhang, 2022).

Findings

As already mentioned, Elden Ring messages may be helpful, misleading or meant to amuse. Literacy in engaging with the messages consists of recognising them as messages, understanding their format and limitation, and knowing how to interact with them (including how to create them). Players also have to interpret meaning in the game location's context. Participant 2 (P2) in Tang (2022) gives an example "... there is an invisible bridge in the mid-air. There are a lot of messages on it. So, I know I can step on it without worrying about falling dead." Participants used their game experience and cross-checked with other sources to decide whether information was trustworthy. For example P2 in Tang (2022) drew on experience from playing similar games, and Participant 4 in Fan (2023), thinking that "Generally speaking, they are fake", checked game walkthroughs (step-by-step guides posted by players online). Some participants themselves left deceptive messages e.g. Tang's (2022) Participant 6: "I will leave the wrong information where it seems right and let others fall for it."

Participants who were players of social deduction games paid attention to various kinds of information to identify whether a fellow player was a traitor and also developed their own strategies for disguising their intentions and identity. For example, Participant 4 in Meng's (2022) study described strategies for "taking control of where the information is directed" to mislead others when playing the traitor, and analysing information from different players for contradictions and inconsistencies. Participant 2 in Wang's (2023) study noted that experienced players developed routines which made it harder to detect falsity. Wang's Participant 8 explained that he listened to the other players' tone of voice, noting any changes. Participants in both studies also observed other players behaviours, to note changes in behaviour indicating they were traitors.

In terms of developing skills in critical evaluation of information, that could carry through to life outside the game, the message was primarily positive. 95% of Meng's questionnaire respondents thought playing Dread Hunger had improved their information literacy in everyday life, and Wang's (2023) participants also reported improvements in confidence and criticality in handling information. However, there were also potential negative outcomes, since players were also learning how to lie effectively and conceal their true intentions.

Findings

These studies make a contribution to IB research in exploring how players use and evaluate player-created information within the game in order to succeed in the game and to inform or mislead others.

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